

Rac-5b

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	XT-2-188-RAC-30%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	1119
Vial:	87	Acq. Method Set:	30%quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	xt 2 188 rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/19/2021 3:11:54 PM CST		
Date Processed:	11/19/2021 3:30:05 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.128	2641884	49.60	170382
2	10.727	2684770	50.40	124272

Asy-5b

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-195-30%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	1119
Vial:	37	Acq. Method Set:	30%quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 2 195
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/19/2021 11:40:50 AM CST		
Date Processed:	11/19/2021 3:35:55 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.135	6411142	96.55	407574
2	10.704	229289	3.45	11098